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Digital Tools as an Essential Factor in Improving the Professional Skills of Graphic Artists-Illustrators

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Abstract: The article examines the role of digital tools in the training of book graphics specialists, highlighting their importance in the professional development of graphic artists-illustrators. It analyzes modern digital technologies, their impact on the illustration

creation process, and the possibilities of integrating them into educational programs. Special attention is given to the development of digital skills essential for book illustration, as well as the use of software for designing and organizing the compositional visual sequence.

Keywords: digital resources, information technologies, illustration, digital graphics, graphic design.

Rezumat: Articolul analizează rolul instrumentelor digitale în formarea specialiștilor în domeniul graficii de carte, care devine un element fundamental pentru dezvoltarea profesională a graficienilor-ilustratori. Autorul analizează tehnologiile digitale moderne în grafica de carte și posibilitatea integrării lor în programele educaționale. O atenție deosebită este acordată dezvoltării competențelor digitale necesare, cu accent pe aplicarea graficii computerizate în realizarea ilustrațiilor de carte și pe conștientizarea relevanței și importanței competențelor acumulate în acest cadru.

Cuvinte-cheie: instrumente digitale, tehnologii informaționale, ilustrație, grafică digitală, design grafic.

The development of computer technologies has a significant impact on the educational process, blurring the boundaries between traditional and digital art and necessitating new forms and approaches to student training. According to F. Martin and J. Ertzberger, digital technologies not only facilitate the learning process but also require its rethinking to adapt to new demands [1]. Consequently, there is a growing need to revise the forms and content of education, as well as to master digital tools that serve as the foundation for professional activities not only in book publishing and graphic design but also in multimedia, animation, and the gaming industry.

Despite high demand and digital competence, illustration teaching methodologies often remain at the level of adapting to new technologies and mechanically mastering digital tools. This raises the question: which digital tools are most effective in the educational process and how they can be integrated into curricula to ensure that students not only acquire technical skills but also develop their creative potential? In our study, we aim to analyze the role of digital tools in the professional training of students by exploring modern technologies and identifying the advantages and disadvantages of their use in book graphics education.

The concept of *digital technologies* is defined as a set of methods, processes, and tools based on the use of computers and software for creating, processing, storing, transmitting, and displaying information. Technologies that encompass the creation, processing, and output of images using digital tools are classified as *computer graphics* [4, p. 28].

Learning computer graphics involves the visualization of digital data in a clear graphical form with artistic and expressive potential, characterizing computer graphics as an essential component of modern technology and art [5, p. 32].

Computer graphics can be divided into several main types: 1) *Raster graphics*, based on pixels or dots that form an image; 2) *Vector graphics*, created using mathematical formulas that define curves; 3) *Fractal graphics*, which rely on mathematical calculations and algorithms to generate self-repeating patterns (fractals) [3, pp. 8-13]. Each of these types has its own characteristics and is applied in various fields of digital art, design, and data visualization.

Digital tools for computer graphics include graphic devices (such as graphics tablets and styluses) as well as a wide range of software and applications [6, pp. 23-25].

A *graphics tablet* is a device that allows users to draw with a stylus directly on a screen or a special surface, displaying the drawing on a computer monitor. The most popular models include professional product lines from Wacom, Huion, XP-Pen, and Apple. These devices vary in specifications such as resolution, stylus

pressure sensitivity, tilt support, response time, and, crucially, size. Tablets come either with or without a built-in screen.

Screenless tablets require some adaptation, as drawing takes place on a special surface while the image is projected onto a monitor. Notable models in this category include the Wacom Intuos Pro, Huion H610 Pro, and XP-Pen Deco.

Screen-equipped tablets, such as the Wacom Cintiq 22, Huion Kamvas Pro, XP-Pen Artist Pro, Pablo Coast, and iPad Pro, offer additional features that significantly streamline and speed up the workflow. These advantages include special shortcut buttons for a quick access, styluses with interchangeable nibs for creating textures and effects, and compatibility with various software applications. The drawing experience on such tablets closely resembles traditional drawing, making them easier to master.

A *graphics editor* is a software designed for creating and editing digital images. Software developers offer a wide range of graphic editors for image creation, processing, and editing. Among the most popular applications are those from Adobe Inc., including *Adobe Photoshop*, *Adobe Illustrator*, and *Adobe InDesign*, as well as *CorelDRAW* by Corel Corporation and *Procreate* by Savage Interactive Pty Ltd.

Adobe Photoshop is one of the most powerful and widely used graphic editors among professional artists and designers in working with raster images. It offers a broad range of tools for drawing and image editing, supporting layers, filters, masks, and effects, which enables the creation of complex compositions.

Adobe Illustrator is a vector graphics editor that allows image scaling without loss of quality. It is widely used in illustration and graphic design, where image clarity is crucial. For artists, it provides an extensive set of tools for freehand drawing with brushes and working with color, including palettes, gradients, and effects. An alternative to *Adobe Illustrator*, also specializing in vector graphics, is *CorelDRAW*.

2. THE INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TOOLS IN CREATING BOOK ILLUSTRATION

Illustration (from the Latin *illustratio, -nis* — lighting, visual representation) is a type of book graphics, which serves as a fundamental element of artistic publications, representing a specific narrative composition embedded within the overall architecture of the book. The application of digital tools in book graphics significantly optimizes the creative process by greatly expanding the technical and graphic means available for realizing artistic ideas through their technical and technological capabilities.

The artistic design of an edition effectively blurs the

line between technical and artistic aspects. According to Vesile Aykaç, computer technologies are not only the equipment and the tools used by graphic artists to create illustrations and book projects, but also an opportunity for their creative realization [2, p. 1011]. Computer graphics offer unique possibilities for creating artistic images that traditional graphic techniques cannot provide, such as the ease of manipulating images, altering their form, silhouette, partially replacing elements, and editing tonal and color solutions. Graphic editors allow the creation of complex, multilayered compositions while preserving the ability to edit individual layers and revert to earlier versions of the composition. Such changes would be difficult to imagine when working with traditional techniques.

At the Graphics specialty at the Academy of Music, Theater, and Fine Arts of the Republic of Moldova, students are offered courses such as *Creative Explorations in Book Graphics and Computer Graphics*, where they learn to use the tools and means of computer graphics by creating a series of illustrations in vector and raster graphics. Practical assignments involve illustrating in various techniques, which fosters the development of creative potential, creating conditions for activating artistic and cognitive activities and enhancing intrinsic motivation for learning. This curriculum helps students develop the ability to effectively relate to traditional graphic techniques and the artistic expressive means of computer graphics in the field of book graphics.

One practical assignment involves developing a graphic series of illustrations in the technique of black-and-white line graphics. To achieve the set objectives, the students are asked to complete the assignment using *vector graphics* in graphic editors such as *Adobe Illustrator* or *CorelDraw*, with the help of a tablet. The task requires creating illustrations with minimal means and limited resources, which is often the case in book illustration. Completing this practical assignment will help students to develop their ability to work with various compositional solutions and effectively organize artistic space.

It is worth noting that the challenge of the assignment lies not only in creating an artistic form solely through line work but also in finding expressiveness in the image. Once the students are restricted from using tonal and color organization, many face difficulties in

organizing the graphic form. Initially, almost all students feel the need for several additional options, such as fills or color backgrounds. This issue can be easily resolved by suggesting that students replace solid fills with a play of lines or textures.

Black-and-white line graphics are easily perceived and remembered, adapting to various artistic styles. However, they require a deep mastery of the tools and a precision in working with vectors and Bézier curves. This skill is crucial for creating high-quality illustrations, where accuracy of lines and contours plays a key role.

The approach of organizing the composition through inversion is another method for working on such a project. The contrast between a large black area and the delicacy of the lines creates a unique atmosphere and expressiveness (Figure no. 1).

Figure no. 1. Vector illustration by Denis Timofeev.

The distinction between creating illustrations in this technique and traditional drawing lies in the flexibility of vector graphics and the speed of transformation without loss of quality or artistic expressiveness. In the context of the educational process and the pressing time constraints, this is a significant advantage. Additionally, the use of various digital brushes, along with pressure sensitivity and tilt control of the stylus, allows to bring greater expression to the digital work and helps achieve a unique artistic image. The artist's technique plays an important role, because even in a digital environment the dynamics of hand movement and approach to work may influence the final result, contributing to greater realism and uniqueness.

Among the main challenges one can note the difficulties presented by composition building. Students often perceive lines as cold and mechanical, which leads to challenges in creating visual dynamics and consequently results in flat and uninspiring illustrations. Vector illustrations require clear and balanced compositions, which can be particularly challenging for students, especially when working with minimal resources (textures, subtle transitions, fills). Vector graphics also demand precision in line drawing, and with

the limitations imposed by software tools and a lack of experience, students struggle to master approaches to stylization, detailing, and creating a unique style.

Another practical assignment involves developing a series of illustrations in raster graphics. Students are tasked with completing this assignment using the graphic editor *Adobe Photoshop* and a graphics tablet. This assignment allows them to combine the technical capabilities of computer graphics by applying filters, effects, and the emotionality of freehand drawing (Figure no. 2).

Figure no. 2. Raster illustration by Kristina Kachurovskaya

In completing this assignment, the students encounter a range of difficulties in mastering tools with advanced capabilities, managing color and layers, and the challenges of working with precise lines and excessive detailing. *Adobe Photoshop* offers artists a powerful set of tools in order to create expressive and detailed illustrations. With a variety of brushes, filters, and plugins that enhance specialized functions and effects, illustrators gain limitless possibilities. However, this can be both an advantage and an obstacle for students. To work effectively with complex tools, masks, and alpha channels, accuracy and high-level practical skills are required.

Creating color illustrations not only necessitates a knowledge of tools, but also requires an understanding of the principles of color and tone. Major issues arise when trying to create harmonious transitions and combine contrasting triads. The multilayered approach in *Adobe Photoshop* allows artists to control every element of the image, which is beneficial for complex illustrations in particular. The use of layers simplifies the editing process and enables the creation of depth and textural effects by combining elements at different levels. Moreover, layers facilitate the management of light and shadow, allowing adjustments to color, saturation, and transparency of individual parts of the illustration. All these features create favorable conditions for unlocking creative potential, as students lose the fear of ruining their work, because most of the graphic editors support the function of restoring earlier versions of a file or undoing several actions.

It is important to note that despite the clear advantages of computer graphics, illustrations created using traditional graphic techniques remain in demand. When creating illustrations in traditional graphic techniques, the artist infuses their unique style, emotional state, mood, and the energy of the creative process into the work, generating a liveliness and expressiveness that are difficult to reproduce with digital tools. Today, many graphic editors strive to replicate traditional artistic tools. For instance, *Adobe Photoshop*, *Adobe Illustrator*, and *Procreate* feature brushes that simulate watercolor, ink pens, pastels, charcoal pencils, and more. Despite their numerous advantages, illustrations created using traditional graphic techniques lose some qualities when processed digitally. In this context, computer graphics become a useful complement, enriching the arsenal of graphic tools (Figure no. 3).

Figure no. 3. Illustration in a mixed technique by Kristina Kachurovskaya.

In order for the computer graphics education to be effective, it is essential to continuously update the curricula in accordance with the latest advancements in computer technology and graphic design. New tools and software are regularly emerging, and their utilization opens up new opportunities for creativity and professional growth. Adapting the educational content enables students not only to master current technologies but also to remain competitive in the job market, which is a crucial aspect of training modern graphic artists. In the future, it is also important to consider the integration of tools for designing and creating interactive digital publications, embedded animation blocks, and elements of augmented virtual reality.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above arguments, it can be concluded that mastering the tools and techniques of computer graphics is indeed fundamental for the professional training of students in the field of book graphics. This allows them to develop not only technical skills and a deeper understanding of the principles of working in graphic editors, but also to expand their creative thinking and the ability to combine traditional artistic approaches and forms with the digital environment. At the same time, doing successful practical work helps them reveal their own creative potential, consolidate gained knowledge, expand the visual vocabulary, and develop the necessary level of professional skills.

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